

TEA

The
European Archaeologist

The newsletter of EAA members for EAA members
Issue 81 – Summer 2024

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Issue 81 – Summer 2024

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Cover

The Colosseum: The beating heart of ancient Rome

In today's world of increasing dependence on technology and the advances it provides, what is the place of the past? The Colosseum was once the Netflix of the ancient world—it was a site of bloody entertainment which inspired Juvenal to write “Give them bread and circuses, and they will never revolt”. Shortened to ‘bread and circuses’ (*panem et circenses*), the metonymic phrase is generally used to refer to superficial appeasement. The Colosseum represents, therefore, both an outlet for and reflection of the interests of the people. It was the beating—and sometimes bloodied—heart of Rome and, as such, holds tremendous appeal to archaeologists.

The Flavian emperors commissioned the Colosseum in the first century AD. It was the site of wildly popular events throughout antiquity, including gladiatorial fights and animal hunts and continues to be a place of spectacles to this day. It has sophisticated stage equipment (including trap doors and mechanisms for flooding the floor for the re-enactments of sea battles) and offered food and drink services in the stands to spectators during the gladiatorial battles. It could accommodate up to 50,000 spectators and is the largest amphitheatre in the world.

The Colosseum started to deteriorate after Valentinian III outlawed gladiatorial contests in 438 AD. It was used as a quarry for building materials during the Middle Ages and Renaissance. In fact, some of its stones were even used in the construction of St. Peter's Basilica. Its charm as an ancient ruin attracted Romantic writers and artists, eventually leading to a revival of interest, methodical excavations and restoration projects. The Amphitheatre, which is still a vibrant and alluring structure today, is a living testament to how human invention and skill have withstood the test of time. Together with the Roman Forum and the Palatine Hill, the Colosseum is part of the [Parco Archeologico del Colosseo](#).

Image and text contributed by Francesca Di Maria

Letter from the Editors

Dear Colleagues,

Europe is once again in the hottest part of the year; we wish all of you a fun, productive, and safe summer whether you are in the field, the office, or on holiday! Just last year our editorial letter highlighted the extreme temperatures and weather that summer will bring. Already it seems that summer 2024 will follow along as a harsh echo of the footsteps of summer 2023. Heatwaves are expected across Europe and beyond, with many countries already experiencing record-breaking heat. In fact, this summer will likely be the hottest ever on record with temperatures exceeding 10C above average already in some places. Unfortunately, this trend shows no sign of changing anytime soon. Please take exceptional precautions while in the field. Be vigilant for signs of [heat stress](#) for yourself and for colleagues!

Of course, summer also brings us closer to the 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome, which is likely to be not only the hottest AM to date, but also the largest. At last count, there are hundreds of [sessions and thousands of presentations](#) from which to choose!

While we wait, however, this issue of *TEA* still has plenty to dig into, including the usual *TEA* fare: the [EAA's July thru October Calendar](#) and [In Case You Missed It](#). As we are focusing on Italy in advance of the 2024 AM (a fact further highlighted by our lovely [cover shot of the Colosseum](#) by Francesca di Maria) this issue also includes interviews with two Italian colleagues: a chat with EAA Official [Maria Taloni](#) (EAA Executive Board) and Meet a Member over *TEA* featuring [Flavia Palazzini](#) (PhD student at Sapienza University of Rome, the host institution for this year's Annual Meeting). In preparation for the Annual Meeting, Francesca Di Maria provides us with [An Archaeologist's Guide to Rome](#), including some great tips on what to see, where to go, how to eat well on a budget and how to organize your visit to get the most out of the Eternal City this summer.

We also include an [Overview of the European Archaeological Council's new guidelines](#) and a Newsflash introducing the [Chantier-Ethique label](#): a code of conduct protocol for conducting and maintaining professional and ethical on-site working conditions. In addition, we take a step into the past of the Silk Road with Anna Radchenko's fascinating cross-disciplinary analysis of [kashi ceramic tiles from sites from the Zaporizhya region of present-date Ukraine](#), which additionally serves as a sharp reminder of the ongoing war in Ukraine and its toll on Ukrainian cultural heritage. In another cross-disciplinary offering, Masahito Tsuboi sheds light on the [evolution of antler size in Cervids](#), revisiting Gould's discussion of allometry (body-scaling in evolutionary contexts) as exemplified in the extreme antler size and morphology of the extinct Irish elk (a prime example of which many of us will recall seeing in the Ulster Museum during last year's AM in Belfast). Speaking of deer, Ali Cameron and Alice Jaspars take us along for the ride as they trace the remarkable provenance of the [Book of Deer](#), a medieval Scottish illuminated manuscript with a complicated history. Rounding out this issue, *TEA* editor Samantha Reiter gives us a review of some recommended summer reading in her review of Jodi Taylor's rollicking time-travel archaeology adventure [Just One Damned Thing after Another](#). Rounding out the issue is a Community Spotlight on the [Society of Africanist Archaeologists \(SAfA\)](#) by Marina Gallinaro and colleagues and an announcement about an upcoming [osteology short course in the UK](#).

Finally, please remember to keep your cameras to hand as you finish up fieldwork or some final sightseeing—once again this year, [TEA has a photojournalism competition](#) on the theme of 'Archaeology: Art or Science?' The due date for submissions has just passed, but we are hopeful to run another competition in 2025! Keep your eyes peeled for prospective shots as well as for further

news! We will be announcing the semi-finalists of this year's competition at the ABM in Rome in just a few weeks' time.

We hope to see you all in Rome.

Best Regards,

Matthew J. Walsh and Samantha S. Reiter

Editors

Calendar for EAA Members

July – October 2024

1 July	deadline for nominations for the European Archaeological Heritage Prize
	deadline for nominations for the Early Career Achievement Prize
2 July	EAA Executive Board Meeting
11 July	Deadline for last Annual Meeting registration cancellation incl. cancellation of paid social events and other booked items (no refund after this date)
31 July (latest)	EAA Secretariat sends out ballot papers to current Members
1 August	EAA Student Award submissions deadline
1 August	TEA photo competition submission deadline
15 August (latest)	EAA Secretariat sends AMBM Report to current Members
30 August	12:00 CEST (noon) deadline for submitting votes in EAA election
28 - 31 August 2024	EAA 2024 Annual Meeting in Rome
27 August	EAA Executive Board Meeting
30 August 2024	2024 Annual Membership Business Meeting (AMBM)
13 September 2024	video recording of the AMBM published on the EAA website and individualised secured access to an electronic ballot provided to all Full Individual Members
13 - 20 September 2023	AMBM voting held <i>per rollam</i>
4 October 2023	results of the AMBM voting published on the EAA website and circulated by e-mail to all Full Individual Members
Early October	Attendance certificates available at submission website
1 October	Deadline for sending in articles and announcements for TEA fall issue

Overview

New Guidelines from the European Archaeological Council (EAC)

Prepared by Marjolein Verschuur on behalf of the EAC

At the 25th annual symposium in Brussels, March 2024 (<https://www.europae-archaeologiae-consilium.org/annual-meeting-2024>) the European Archaeological Council launched a series of new guidance documents which are directly relevant to the archaeology and cultural heritage. Here, we give a brief overview of those various frameworks.

The European Archaeological Council (EAC) is a democratic network open to all national bodies charged with the management of the archaeological heritage throughout Europe. The primary mission of the EAC is to support the management of archaeological heritage throughout Europe and to serve the needs of national archaeological heritage management agencies by providing a forum for these agencies to establish closer and more structured co-operation and exchange of information. In order to do so, the EAC hosts a themed annual symposium focused on issues for or pressures on archaeological management which transcend state borders. Furthermore, it convenes specialist working groups whose voluntary members undertake specific research and develop international guidance and advice in response to members' needs. The editions of the guidance launched in 2024 were all developed to address issues raised in the [Amersfoort Agenda](#) and the EAC Making Choices members' survey undertaken in 2017.

Guidelines

[The Benefits of Development-Led Archaeology in Europe and Beyond](#)

This guideline consists of a short overview of the subject as well as a longer document with illustrative case-studies. The reports present nine tangible public benefits which can be derived from development-led archaeological investigation, illustrated by genuine case studies from across Europe and beyond. It is designed to act as a resource for all archaeological heritage managers, archaeologists, and other stakeholders to help make the case for supporting development-led archaeology, and to help shape investigation projects to get the most out of them for the public. It recognises that the benefits of archaeology go far beyond its inherent value in creating knowledge about our shared past, creating many other societal and scientific benefits. It demonstrates the very small additional cost of development-led archaeology at the state level and concludes that this cost is outweighed by the positive benefits which can be realised if archaeological work is planned into projects from the outset.

[Revisiting the Valletta Convention for the Digital Age. Position statement on archiving primary archaeological data](#)

There is a significant disparity between the value of archaeological data and their handling within heritage management practice. This imbalance threatens the preservation of cultural heritage being continuously removed from the landscape and transformed into archives of (digital) archaeological documentation. To mitigate the risks, systemic changes are necessary. These changes require political decision-making to provide the resources, a clear framework and the tools to create a sustainable and meaningful environment for archaeological archiving, leading to the highest possible social benefit. The EAC proposes a set of basic principles for the handling of primary documentary archives and recommends practical measures to be taken in the legislative and organisational framework and derived archaeological practice. The proposed measures can be applied as widely as possible as a basic standard of care for archaeological cultural heritage.

Preceding this, two other guidelines on archaeological archiving were published: *A Standard and Guide to Best Practices in Archaeological Archiving in Europe* (2014) and *Guidance on Selection in Archaeological Archiving* (2021).

[The Value of Developing a Research Framework](#)

This short document provides the strategic context that supports the value and role of research frameworks in fostering a coordinated research culture and embedding a research/evidence-based approach that underpins heritage management, regardless of the different political, legal, administrative and economic contexts of individual states. This includes supporting decision making and broadening public benefit to include social and communal values as well as the research dividend. The document is aimed at those people who are responsible for commissioning, funding or developing research frameworks. It can be used to support the creation of a business case for developing a research framework and sets out the key principles that should be considered in doing so.

Further guidance publications are in preparation and will be released later in 2024.

[Articulating the Significance of Archaeological Sites \(forthcoming\)](#)

The EAC Making Choices survey identified a desire for guidance on the articulation of the significance of heritage assets to ensure that the values of each site are clearly conveyed when needed. Traditions differ somewhat between countries in Europe. This guideline poses key questions; are all cultural remains equally valuable and, if not, what determines differences in value? Can remains have more value in some regions than others? What tools are available to help come to a conclusion in this regard? Can the value of a site change over time both for the public or even archaeologists? On what grounds can heritage managers require research due to development? Should a whole site be excavated or ought one excavate partially on sites of “lesser significance”? How does one evaluate such a decision? This guidance provides a discussion on the philosophical problems heritage managers face when dealing with the significance of sites and gives a good overview of the methods used for evaluating significance in different European countries. The EAC is organising a session at the 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome on this subject (#592, *Decision-making and Assessing and Articulating Archaeological Significance*).

[*The Use of Airborne Laser Scanning \(Lidar\) in Archaeology \(forthcoming\)*](#)

The EAC Airborne Laser Scanning (lidar) Guidelines are designed to help cultural heritage managers, specialist practitioners and students who work with airborne lidar with the archaeological and heritage projects in which they use lidar. These focused guidelines support readers to efficiently access the information which is most relevant to their needs and to explore further publications and information. The guidelines provide an overview of key considerations when commissioning an airborne laser scanned survey (ALS) for archaeological and heritage applications, for creating and using ALS data for these applications and for designing and managing workflows and projects that take advantage of these data.

The guide is divided into four parts. The first summarises sensor technology and data acquisition, preparing users to commission data and assess the reuse potential of archived data. The second sets out good practice for post-acquisition data processing and analysis. The third outlines guidance for reporting and archiving data. The fourth reviews specific applications of airborne laser survey within the heritage sector and the benefits and challenges of using A data for historic landscape studies in a range of environments.

[*Developing Research Frameworks \(forthcoming\)*](#)

This guide provides a practical guide to support the development or update of a research framework. It is not meant to be prescriptive means of setting out the ‘correct’ way to develop a framework. Instead, it covers variation in types of frameworks (including scope and content) and establishes a number of steps or considerations that can be of assistance in thinking through all the different aspects of creating a framework. The guidance also contains multiple case study reviews of existing research frameworks to get a quick overview of the work done by other countries for inspiration when creating or updating a new research framework. This guidance is designed to support everyone involved in the process including those commissioning a framework, those running a project and those in the process of building one.

At the annual symposium in 2024, the EAC asked its members what they thought the priorities were for Heritage Management that the EAC could help address in the next five years. Building on these results, the EAC will continue to provide guidance and advice for its members and colleagues in the future.

NB: All guidelines are published on the digital repository Zenodo. The direct links included above can also be found on the [dedicated page on the EAC website](#).

Bibliography

Making Choices: Valletta, Development, Archaeology and Society. A Report of the ‘Making Choices’ Working Group of the Europae Archaeologiae Consilium (EAC, 2018)
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10695784

In Case You Missed It...

Joana Valdez-Tullett

EAA Social Media Editor

[Kinship and ancestry of the Celts in Baden-Wurtemberg](#)

[Roman snail dye found in UK for first time](#)

[Archaeology team discovers a 7,000-year-old settlement in Serbia](#)

[Lasers reveal prehistoric Irish monuments that may have been 'pathways for the dead'](#)

[Archaeologists discover what may be the oldest known piece of bread](#)

[Earliest directly dated rock art from Patagonia reveals socioecological resilience to mid-Holocene climate](#)

[A portrait of the past: What is the Archaeological Atlas of France?](#)

[A New Study on a 16th-Century Shipwreck in Portugal reveals its valuable cargo](#)

[DNA says you're related to a Viking, a medieval German Jew or a 1700s enslaved African? What a genetic match really means](#)

[Aboriginal people made pottery and sailed to distant offshore islands thousands of years before Europeans arrived](#)

[Carbonised Herculaneum papyrus reveals burial place of Plato](#)

All images used in "In Case You Missed It" are from FlatIcon (www.flaticon.com)

Chat with EAA Official over TEA

Maria Taloni

Institution: National Research Council of Italy – Institute of Heritage Science (researcher)

Position in the EAA: Executive Board member (since 2020)

EAA Member since: 2014

Image at left courtesy M. Taloni

TEA: Why do you do archaeology/How did you decide to do it?

M. Taloni: My passion for archaeology--particularly Classics with an archaeological focus--blossomed in high school thanks to an inspiring Latin and Greek teacher. A specific turning point came during my junior year, when we delved deeply into Greek tragedy, specifically Sophocles' *Oedipus Rex*. I vividly recall visiting the library and getting engrossed in Eric Dodds' *The Greeks and the Irrational*. This book sparked a fascination with the *École des hautes études en sciences sociales'* approach to historical-anthropological studies. It struck me that this methodology could be incredibly relevant to archaeological investigations.

Imagine my surprise when, upon entering university, I discovered that the archaeological school led by Professor Bruno d'Agostino was already putting these very theories into practice in studying funerary contexts! They were applying a post-processual perspective to the historical-archaeological study of the ancient world. Furthermore, I have always held a strong belief in the ethical and civic responsibility that archaeology carries in contemporary society. Even to this day, this conviction remains the driving force behind my archaeological pursuits.

TEA: How do you see archaeology changing in the future?

M. Taloni: Archaeology has changed a lot in the 20 years since I started university, and I think this trend will continue in the near future and will even accelerate. The main novelty is the increasing integration between archaeology and 'hard' sciences and new technologies.

In addition, it is worth underlining the growing need for greater multidisciplinary and interdisciplinarity. For me, this has always been natural because of my cultural background and having attended an experimental high school that integrated subjects such as economics and law with traditional classical subjects.

At university, just to give an example, professors still used slides with a projector as an iconographic support for their lessons; now we can use generative AI. On the first excavations, surveys were done by hand with tape and plumb line; now we can also use the most modern 3D surveying technologies. Who knows what the future holds? I cannot wait to find out what the next 20 years hold for archaeology!

Image above shows Taloni at the Archaeological Park of Cerveteri and Tarquinia, Etruscan necropolis of Banditaccia (Cerveteri), inside the Tomb of the Reliefs. Image courtesy of M. Taloni.

TEA: What is the biggest issue facing archaeology today?

M. Taloni: The greatest challenge facing archaeology today and in the future is and will be to integrate archaeological practice with territorial planning and the management of archaeological cultural heritage, actively participating in the decision-making and administrative process at both local and national levels.

Linked to this is also the possibility of involving citizens as much as possible as real heritage communities in line with the spirit of the Faro Convention (which states that cultural heritage is an integral part of the identity of a territory with an inner value that contributes to the improvement of society and to the well-being and quality of daily life).

TEA: What is the one piece of gear that you cannot live without in the field?

M. Taloni: For sure in the field, I cannot live without my English trowel, the very same one that I have carefully preserved for years.

TEA: If you could go back in time, would you go? Where and when?

M. Taloni: If I could go back in time, I would certainly choose to live in one of the great Etruscan poleis on the Tyrrhenian Sea, *Caere/Kaisra* or *Tarchna* in the 7th or 6th century BC, a period of great political-social changes and cultural and commercial exchanges. I imagine putting myself in the shoes of

Larthia, the owner of the rich Regolini-Galassi tomb in *Caere*, and enjoying the freedom and autonomy of an aristocrat, as well as culture.

In reality, from a geographical point of view, I would not have to move much because I live in Ladispoli, which corresponds as the location to one of the three great ports of *Caere*, *Alsium*, together with *Punicum* (present-day Santa Marinella) and the famous port-sanctuary of *Pyrgi* (Santa Severa), a few kilometers on the sea from the ancient city of *Caere* (now Cerveteri).

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

M. Taloni: Firstly, I would advise only considering pursuing archaeology at university if you are genuinely passionate and determined to undertake the studies. One should be fully aware that it is a lengthy and challenging path. However, do not be deterred by the fear of not securing a permanent and stable job immediately after graduation.

Secondly, I would encourage you to not limit yourself to a single path and to not be disheartened by initial setbacks and difficulties. The field of archaeology is now extremely broad and offers diverse career prospects, particularly due to advancements in technology and the growing desire for community involvement. There are opportunities beyond academia, research and statal heritage management.

Similarly, I can attest to having undertaken all possible archaeological jobs that came my way before finding a stable position, which only materialized ten years after graduation following a national competition for an archaeological officer role at the Ministry. Currently, I hold a research position (also secured through a national competition), but I previously worked as a freelance field archaeologist, museum and education worker, tour guide, high school teacher of Italian literature, history, Latin and Greek and postdoctoral researcher.

Image at left: A find from a rescue excavation in suburban Rome. Photo courtesy of M. Taloni

TEA: What, in your opinion, is the role of a museum today? How has this changed?

M. Taloni: In the past, museums were primarily seen as custodians of history and culture. Their focus was on collecting, preserving and displaying artefacts. They served as repositories of the past, with a one-way flow of information from the museum to the visitor. Today, museums are evolving into much more dynamic and vital institutions for learning, engagement and community. My own experiences working at the Archaeological Park of Cerveteri and Tarquinia—particularly within its two museums—perfectly exemplify this shift. Here, education, the inclusivity of diverse audiences, digitalization, integration and collaboration are at the forefront. These are the very words that come to mind when I consider both my role in museums and the evolving role museums play within their communities. This shift has also impacted the role of researchers. Studies today are conducted with a more audience-oriented approach. We can no longer remain isolated in our ‘ivory towers’ without considering the needs of society. Research findings must be shared and be demonstrably useful for the public good.

TEA: Was archaeology always your dream job? What else did you consider? Why did you end up choosing archaeology in the end?

M. Taloni: I must admit that I never solely focused on work during my university studies, and I never in my wildest dreams did I imagine that I would end up working in heritage protection at the Ministry, let alone as a researcher at the CNR! Looking back on the long road I have travelled, I can say that I am indeed satisfied with my achievements.

However, I always had backup plans B, C and D in case I was unable to secure a job as an archaeologist. As mentioned earlier, I have held various jobs, and I would have undoubtedly pursued a career as a high school teacher. Sharing my experiences and passion for the ancient world with younger generations has always been a joy for me; my students have always appreciated my enthusiasm and the attention I paid to them.

And if even this option had not materialized, I would have continued working as a field archaeologist and in public outreach as a tour guide.

In short, I would not have fretted too much.

And, perhaps, it is because of this attitude that I can say that archaeology chose me, not the other way around...

Image of archaeological drawing of a house urn from one of Vulci's necropolises during recent archaeological excavations. Image courtesy of M. Taloni.

Meet a Member over *TEA*

Flavia Palazzini

Institution: Sapienza Università di Roma

Position: PhD Student

EAA Member since: 2021

Image at left courtesy of F. Palazzini

***TEA:* How did you know that archaeology was what you wanted to do?**

F. Palazzini: My realization that I wanted to pursue archaeology occurred somewhat unexpectedly. After finishing high school, I opted to study philology at university, driven by my interest in classics. However, it was during this time that a professor of Roman history—who was also an archaeologist—took our class on a field trip to the Roman Forum. I distinctly remember her examining a wall and explaining how the measurements and positioning of the bricks in the structures help archaeologists to determine a date, even in the absence or uncertainty of written records. Though simple, this information was eye-opening for me. It made me realize that I wanted to explore history through a more hands-on and practical approach, and that archaeology was the way to do that.

***TEA:* How does archaeology affect your daily life?**

F. Palazzini: Archaeology has deeply influenced my daily life, fostering frequent travel and connecting me with people from diverse countries and backgrounds, each with unique stories and experiences that helped me broaden my perspectives. It has transformed me significantly. Although I was once more cautious about venturing beyond my comfort zone, I now eagerly keep my suitcase packed! I relish exploring new places and engaging in fieldwork and I cherish the camaraderie of post-excavation gatherings. These experiences not only enhance professional expertise but also consistently foster personal growth and transformation across the board.

***TEA:* Describe your workspace in five words or less**

F. Palazzini: (Full of) sherds, books, drawings and... dust.

***TEA:* What is the one piece of gear that you can't live without in the field?**

F. Palazzini: If I could choose just one item, I would say an extra pen. Pens have a way of disappearing during documentation, and I tend to leave them in the most unexpected corners of the excavation!

Image at right: Excavation at Monte Croce Guardia (Marche, AN): Photo by A. Conte, with permission.

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

F. Palazzini: My research primarily focuses on the recovery of archaeological legacy datasets and the establishment of best practices for analysing past excavations, from archival research to dissemination. By retrieving and digitizing this information, my goal is to reconstruct the narratives of archaeological contexts that warrant deeper understanding. A significant case study I have focused on is the site of Torre Castelluccia in southern Italy, near Taranto. This site is currently experiencing degradation due to the absence of concrete conservation plans and faces threats from urban development pressures.

I consider the most crucial aspect of my work to be the effort to recover and highlight these types of neglected archaeological sites, which urgently need preservation. This endeavour aims not only to bring the sites to the attention of the scientific community, but also to the local community, thereby raising awareness of their cultural significance. I aspire for my work to serve as a catalyst for renewed research and conservation initiatives, ensuring that these sites are protected and valued for future generations.

TEA: What is the biggest issue facing archaeology today?

F. Palazzini: One of the biggest issues facing archaeology today is the preservation and protection of archaeological sites and cultural heritage in the face of increasing development pressures, environmental changes and the lack of funding for new research. As urbanization expands, archaeological sites face the threat of destruction and irreversible damage. Additionally, climate change poses risks and changing weather patterns affect fragile archaeological remains. Addressing these challenges requires collaborative efforts among archaeologists, stakeholders and local communities to implement effective preservation strategies and strengthen protection.

Image at left: Geophysical survey in Molise. Photo by F. Palazzini.

TEA: How do you see archaeology changing in the future?

F. Palazzini: In the near future, I foresee that archaeology will continue embracing interdisciplinary approaches, integrating archaeological data with other scientific and analytical methods such as genetics, environmental science and computer science. New technologies will develop further: innovations such as gaming, 3D reconstructions and immersive experiences will be employed to captivate the public, fostering wider participation and heightened interest in the field. Additionally, there will likely be a growing trend toward automation in data analysis through the application of machine learning and artificial intelligence, leading to developments that are difficult to fully envision today. While these technologies can significantly advance research (as evidenced by current applications), it is crucial to utilize them as tools rather than as ends in themselves. Maintaining a focus on the interpretive dimension and the potential for historical reconstruction—which remain the archaeologist's responsibility and are directly tied to their expertise—is essential.

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

F. Palazzini: As a doctoral student myself, still navigating my academic journey, I can closely relate to those just beginning in archaeology. My advice to new archaeologists is to actively pursue a variety of field activities and internships, exploring areas beyond their initial specialization. Embrace curiosity and openness to new methodologies and perspectives, as these experiences can uncover unexpected interests and significantly shape your future research direction. For instance, despite my background in classical studies, I have found a strong interest in pre- and protohistoric archaeology through active research and fieldwork. Needless to say, I am very happy with my choice to “try something different”! Moreover, it's crucial to acknowledge that the academic environment can be challenging. Upholding ethical standards and nurturing collaborative relationships are paramount. By promoting fairness, we can build trust and create a supportive community, which serves as the foundation for a more rewarding working environment. As Anne Galloway—cited by Emily Bernhardt in the renowned essay "Being Kind"—aptly put it: "Everyone here is smart, distinguish yourself by being kind".

Image at left: Field survey at Samo (Calabria, RC). Photo by N. Talotta, with permission.

Newsflash

Chantier-Ethique: A Label to Reduce Discrimination on Archaeological Digs

Isabelle Algrain¹, Laura Mary², Béline Pasquini and Ségolène Vandeveldé³

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³ Université Paris 1 Panthéon–Sorbonne

⁴ Université du Québec à Chicoutimi et Université de Sherbrooke

Archaeological excavations are conducive to the development of systemic discrimination, such as sexism, homophobia, ableism and racism. As most of us are already aware, the work—which is often physically demanding—is usually done in groups over several weeks (or even months) in a ‘timeless’ environment. Several studies in recent years have highlighted the extent of discrimination on digs (e.g., Coltofean-Arizancu et al., 2023 with a bibliography of previous studies). The *Chantier-Ethique* (lit. ‘ethical excavation’) label, developed by the [Paye ta Truelle Collective](#) and the [Archéo-Ethique Association](#) aims to help site managers reduce discrimination on their archaeological digs.

How does it work?

The principle of the label is simple: it offers site managers a code of conduct to be signed by everyone working on the site, regardless of the duration of their stay or their hierarchical level. This code comes with a short manual, a tool primarily intended for the site manager which provides a step-by-step guide for handling reports of problematic behavior. When a person is not trained to deal with discrimination, they may make mistakes even with the best of intentions (minimizing incidents or confronting the potential victim with the aggressor are among the most common errors). In addition to the code, this manual should also be read and understood by everyone participating in the

excavation. From the moment of application for participating in an excavation, diggers are then aware that site management is vigilant with regards to this topic. The code and manual are available at [this address](#) in French, English, and Spanish (the English translation of the manual is currently in progress). To join the program, one must complete a short form and send it to the association before the start of archaeological work.

Is it really effective?

The effectiveness of the *Chantier-Ethique* label relies entirely on the goodwill and commitment of the site manager. The initial premise is that a person who voluntarily chooses to adopt it is genuinely aiming to improve working conditions on their site. Since it was launched in 2019, several dozen sites have chosen to adhere to the movement. Thus far in 2024, there are 23 participating digs (primarily in France and Belgium but also in a few non-French-speaking countries, such as Cyprus and the United States).

Over the past few years, some site managers have asked excavators fill out anonymous evaluation forms about the code. The responses indicate that the perception of the initiative is generally positive. However, criticisms have emerged, mainly concerning the effectiveness of a label that lacks both control mechanisms and enforcement capabilities.

Several problematic digs have been reported to the association since the creation of the code. In all cases, these were excavations that had falsely claimed the label: they used the logo in their communications and pretended to be members, but they had never officially applied for membership with the Archéo-Ethique Association. In all these cases, the site managers were contacted, urged to stop using the *Chantier-Ethique* logo and encouraged to seek training on discrimination issues.

On the part of the *Paye Ta Truelle* Collective and the Archéo-Ethique Association, a procedure has also been established for cases in which an *actually* certified site is reported for not adhering to the spirit of the code. In such cases, managers and supervisors will be required to undergo training on discrimination. If they refuse, the label will be revoked. Efforts are currently underway to further improve the initiative, including provisions for site managers to indicate who is designated as discrimination officers, whether it is a first-time certification or a renewal and whether accessible toilets will be available during the excavation.

The list of certified sites is available on the [association's website](#). Do not hesitate to join or to implement a similar initiative on your own dig!

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Special Section

An Archaeologist's Guide to Rome

Francesca Di Maria

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Welcome to An Archaeologist's Guide to Rome, the city that stole my heart during my university days! Together, we will embark on an exciting journey starting from Sapienza University of Rome (my alma mater). From there, we will explore the city's charms, navigate around construction and revel in the beauty and history of Rome. Prepare for a blend of history, fun and—of course—delicious food!

Rome is vast, and there is so much to see. Here is what you will need for a perfect day of exploring:

- Comfortable walking shoes: You will be doing a lot of strolling.
- Light clothing: Rome can get quite warm, especially in the summer.
- Sunscreen: Protect yourself from the strong sun.
- Water bottle: Stay hydrated! One of the great things about Rome is its many *nasoni*: the characteristic public fountains found all over the city where you can refill your bottle with fresh, free water. Some areas (like near the Colosseum) even have dispensers for still and sparkling water where you can also re-charge your phone!

Sapienza University of Rome: Our Starting Point

Sapienza University was established in 1303. As such, it is one of the oldest and most prestigious universities in Europe. The main campus (known as the *Città Universitaria*, or 'university city') was designed by architect Marcello Piacentini and inaugurated in 1935. It is a true city within the city ([Where Am I? | Sapienza Università di Roma \(uniroma1.it\)](#)), complete with educational buildings, administrative offices, libraries and museums. Besides the historical campus on Piazzale Aldo Moro in the San Lorenzo neighbourhood, Sapienza has various faculty and department buildings and offices in different areas of Rome, as well as university centres in other parts of the Lazio region.

But it is on the main campus that the EAA's 2024 AM will take place.

To reach Sapienza:

- From Termini Station: It is a short walk (less than 20 minutes).

- From Tiburtina Station: You can take the metro B to Policlinico Station and walk for about 15 minutes, or hop on buses 71, 163, 448, or 545 to the Verano stop, or 492 to the De Lollis/Verano stop. It is less than a 5-minute walk from there.

Inside and around the *Città Universitaria*

Within the university walls, you can explore several museums (check out the Sapienza Museum Map [Musei | Polo museale \(uniroma1.it\)](#)) and enjoy a coffee at the bar near the main entrance. Remember to fill up your water bottle at one of the many fountains around campus!

The vibrant neighbourhood surrounding the university is known as San Lorenzo. It offers a lively atmosphere with plenty of bars, cafes and eateries perfect for students and visitors alike. Around campus, you can find a lot of bars for takeaway food (i.e. [Livio](#), [Bar Leonardi](#), [C'era una Volta il Caffè](#) or [Bar dei Sanniti](#)). If you prefer a sit-down meal, visit some typical Roman restaurants (i.e. [Tram Tram](#), [Osteria da Marcello](#) or [Osteria A Piedi Pari](#)) where you can try different dishes like *pasta alla carbonara* (pasta with cream, bacon, black pepper and parmesan), *pasta all'amatriciana* (pasta with bacon, tomato and pecorino romano), *cacio e pepe* (pasta with cheese and pepper) and *gricia* (pasta with guanciale, pecorino romano, and black pepper). I also recommend you give Roman pizza a go. It is thin and crispy unlike the Neapolitan style, but it is equally delicious! Some good places to try it are [Pizzeria Formula 1](#) and [Pizzeria L'economica](#).

A Glimpse into Rome's Timeless Charm

Rome is truly unique, with a continuous history stretching back to its legendary founding on April 21, 753 BC. This rich past has created a city where you can capture Roman, medieval, Renaissance and contemporary elements in a single photograph. This blend of different eras has given Rome its well-deserved epithet as the "Eternal City".

In the following, I will give you a taste of some of my favourite spots to visit by hopping on the Metro A and B lines, along with tips for enjoying the city to the fullest. First, a few caveats, however. Obviously, it is impossible to visit everything in a single day. Here, I will suggest some routes, varying in length and distance from Sapienza, to see as much as possible in a single go. Feel free—as I am—to stop and detour at museums or interesting sites. However, if do plan on visiting a specific museum, I highly recommend buying a ticket online ahead of time with the skip-the-line option.

Metro A Adventures

Termini Station: This is where the A and B lines meet and is a short walk from Sapienza's main entrance. In front of the main entrance of Termini station, you can easily spot the Roman National Museum (*Museo Nazionale Romano*) at the *Palazzo Massimo*, a treasure trove of ancient Roman art

and artefacts. Besides it are the *Terme di Diocleziano* (the baths of Diocletian), the largest and most impressive bath complex in Rome. Inside that structure is a museum with pre-roman findings as well.

Repubblica Stop: Nearby, you can explore the *Basilica di Santa Maria degli Angeli e dei Martiri* (the basilica of Saint Mary of the Angels and of the Martyrs) and its solar calendar.

San Giovanni Stop: A bit farther than Termini but still within walking distance from the *Città Universitaria* via the lateral entrance on Via de Lollis. Here, you will find Porta Maggiore, one of the ancient city gates included in the Aqua Claudia Aqueduct. A little further, you'll discover the Basilica di San Giovanni in Laterano, the cathedral church of Rome, which is stunning in its grandeur.

Flaminio Stop: Stroll through *Piazza del Popolo* (the People's Square), head up to Pincio Terrace for some of the best panoramic views of Rome before a meander down the Via del Corso. The Via del Corso is a bustling shopping street leading to many attractions with side streets leading to Piazza di Spagna, Piazza Navona, the Pantheon and the Trevi Fountain. Do not miss [Giolitti Gelateria](#), a must-stop for delicious gelato (my current favourite flavor? Champagne – it's fabulous!).

Piazza Venezia: Admire the *Altare della Patria* (literally the "Alter of the Fatherland") behind the metro construction block built over the turn of the last century to honour Victor Emmanuel II, the first kind of a unified Italy.

From here, choose your next adventure:

- Trastevere: Take the tram for a lively atmosphere, perfect for wandering through narrow, cobblestone streets or strolling along the riverside. (At night, it is even more enchanting).
- Capitoline Hill: from the *Altare della Patria* turn right, climb the steps and visit the [Musei Capitolini](#) (Capitoline Hill museums) or continue along the road and to the Teatro Marcello. From there, you can either follow the street downhill to the *Bocca della Verità* (Mouth of Truth) church and Circo Massimo or explore the Jewish Ghetto ending at Largo di Torre Argentina archaeological area.
- Via dei Fori Imperiali: from the *Altare della Patria*, turn left and go admire and visit Colonna and *Mercati di Traiano* (the Market of Trajan), the *Fori Imperiali* (the Imperial Forum) and/or the Colosseum (where you can transfer to Metro B).

Ottaviano Stop: Visit Vatican City and the [Vatican Museum](#). It is important to know that you would be well served to book tickets in advance. From there, you can easily reach the Castel Sant'Angelo. Nearby, on the other side of the river, you will find many typical Roman restaurants like [Osteria da Fortunata](#) and [Da Tonino - Trattoria Bassetti](#) .

Metro B Adventures

Colosseo Stop: The first thing you will see upon exiting the metro station is the iconic and breathtaking Colosseum, the *Arco di Costantino* (the Arc of Constantine) and the main entrance to the *Fori*

Imperiali. Do not miss Michelangelo’s magnificent statue of Moses in San Pietro in Vincoli Church and—if you book a visit—the Domus Aurea, Nero’s Golden House.

From here, you can either take the metro to Circo Massimo stop or take a pleasant walk to Piazza Venezia, following Ara Coeli Street to arrive (as describe above) at Circo Massimo.

Once you arrive to the Giuseppe Mazzini Statue, Climb the hill via the road on the right behind the statue to reach the *Giardino degli Aranci* (literally the Garden of Orange Trees) for a fantastic view of Rome. Next, peek through the Aventine Keyhole for a unique view of St. Peter’s Basilica, only a few meters away from the garden.

Discovering Rome’s Churches along the road

Every church in Rome is a masterpiece of art and architecture. Step inside to admire the frescoes and intricate designs. Many churches incorporate elements from ancient Roman buildings, like the one next to Capitoline Hill or the one in Verano Square. Just remember that Rome is a traditional city and will expect visitors to the churches to dress modestly. That means you should avoid short skirts or shorts and sleeveless tops (or just have a light shawl in your bag to cover any bare shoulders).

Figure 1. An archaeologist’s map of Rome by Francesca Di Maria. Inset photos by Francesca Di Maria, Erika Ergasti and Flavia Palazzini.

Tips for a Great Experience

- Early bird advantage: Start your day early to beat the crowds at popular sites like the Colosseum and the Vatican, and to enjoy a few hours without the extremely warm temperatures.
- Local eats: Do not miss out on Roman cuisine. Try dishes like *cacio e pepe*, *carbonara* and *supplì*.
- Where to go for an evening drink? When the sun sets and it is time for a refreshing drink, here is the lowdown: If you are up for a lively student atmosphere (though it might be quieter in August), head to San Lorenzo, Piazza Bologna, or the Pigneto quarter. However, if you are craving a more romantic vibe—and do not mind spending a little more—Trastevere, Campo dei Fiori and the Monti Quarter are where you want to be! Sip, relax, and soak in the charming ambiance of Rome at night!
- Hidden Gems: Sometimes the best experiences come from wandering off the beaten path. Explore side streets and lesser-known spots for a more authentic city feel (this is my favourite way to visit Rome – I love getting lost in its side streets).

Rome is a city that invites you to explore, discover and fall in love with its timeless beauty. Since it is impossible to describe all of Rome in just a few words, I have created a map to give you a few points. See Figure 1. Along with the metro and tram routes to Trastevere (dotted lines), I have marked in red the paths I usually take when strolling around the city. Sometimes, I randomly wander into little alleyways and get lost, but that's part of Rome's charm. I won't lie – I have often had to rely on Google Maps to find my way back! The numbers highlight just a few of the countless wonders you can see in Rome. I hope this guide helps you enjoy the city as much as I do.

Buon viaggio!

Research Overview

Notes along the Silk Road: What Mineralogy Can Tell Us about Trust

Anna Radchenko

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Figure 2. A schematic map of the Silk Road showing larger urban nodes. Kinski Vody, the site under discussion, is shown at the top left. Image by Simon Radchenko, used here with permission.

In 2008 and 2012, I was lucky enough to volunteer for archaeological fieldwork at Mechet’-Mohyla (archaeologically known as the settlement of Kinski Vody) near Orikhiv in the Zaporizhzhia region of Ukraine. See Figure 2. Volunteering was primarily possible thanks to the openness of the NGO “New Archaeological School.” Fieldwork supervisor Mykhailo Elnikov spoke emphatically about the northern branch of the Silk Road, which passed through the Zaporizhzhia region and gave rise to a dozen Golden Horde cities. Those cities experienced an era of cultural prosperity in the 13th and 14th centuries (Elnikov 2016; 2018a; 2018b; 2019; 2022). In the 14th century, the ancient settlement on the left bank of the Konka River could boast a population of about 20,000 people, as evidenced by archaeological research and the remains of several large buildings in the area. See Figure 3. I took part in the excavation of one of the structures (presumably a mosque) which sits on a 20x20 m foundation built of local stone and brick. The fact that the structure belongs to the Golden Horde epoch was indicated by many fragments of kashi mosaic tiles. Kashi ceramics emerged in Iran in the 11th-12th centuries as an imitation of expensive Chinese porcelain products and later became a special ceramic group. Such tiles were made of high-quality porcelain-like quartz mass and became widespread between the 12th and 17th centuries throughout Iran, Central Asia, Transcaucasia, and areas touched by the Golden

Horde. The many colours and differently-shaped fragments of kashi were mounted on walls in fresh mortar following a clearly thought-out pattern: the so-called coat. At the site of Kinski Vody, some of the remnants of the coat ornaments can be partially reconstructed, evidencing the presence of a fascinating decoration. However, up until present, scholars have little (if any) knowledge of what the tiles paints were made of, what pigments were used for turquoise, blue, green, yellow or red glaze, and where such products might have been sourced.

Figure 3. Mausoleum in Kinski Vody. Retrieved on 31.04.2024 from “Seven mosques in Zaporizhyya region”. *Islam v Ukraini*. Available [here](#).

With this question in mind, a research project was born. I am sincerely grateful to Professor Mykhailo Elnikov of Zaporizhzhia National University for providing the samples. Elnikov presented part of the results as an addendum to his detailed classification and analysis of kashi building ceramics from the Kinski Vody settlement (Elnikov 2017). The results of the study were published in a small edited volume in Russian (Radchenko 2017). However, this research is still useful for a broader audience as a study of the application of mineralogical research methods in archaeology. This is doubly important as the work was done in unoccupied Crimea in the Crimean branch of the Ukrainian State Geological Exploration Institute (Simferopol). This was where my parents – Igor Palkin and Olena Palkina worked, and which has now been completely destroyed. I am very grateful to them and other employees of the Institute for the opportunity to conduct these studies.

Due to the full-scale Russian invasion which has been going on for more than two years now, the territory of the monument has been subjected to continuous shelling and destruction. It is unclear whether we will ever be able to supplement the existing information by returning to the study of the settlement and its buildings. This provides even greater motivation to present this study to a wider range of readers.

Materials and methods

We studied mosaic fragments from the ornamentation of the public building of the Kinski Vody settlement, excavated in the summer of 2012. The mosaic pieces have the same quartz base and were covered with a coloured layer made of glaze. See Figure 4.

Figure 4. Fragments of the mosaic under study in situ. Photo by Anna Radchenko.

Elnikov (2017) points out that the basis of kashi (and the majority of the building ceramics at the Kinski Vody settlement) belong to friable kasha, which is typical of other Golden Horde centres. Referring to the Koval, Elnikov writes that kashi is mostly quartz sand ground into powder, with the possible

addition of fluxes (a small amount of white clay, lime) and mixed with an aqueous solution of glue of animal or vegetable origin and fused at a temperature of 900–1000°C.

The chemical compound of the kashi mosaics from the Kinski Vody site is mainly quartz (river alluvial sand) with a high content of silica (SiO₂) in the range of 90.42–93.83 %, with additions of clay – 0.92–2.92 % and lime – 4.14–6.48 %. There is an insignificant amount of micro admixtures (total mass about 2–2.33 %) of rock-forming minerals in the composition: quartz, clay, and sometimes potassium feldspar (Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MgO). Kashi bricks from Kinski Vody featured larger sand grains than mosaic tiles, with quartz and magnetite grains up to 1 mm in size (Elnikov 2017). The colour of the Kinski Vody kashi also varies slightly (dirty-white, yellowish-gray, light gray). According to Koval (2010), there is no connection between the colour of kashi and the place of its production: those typical of the Golden Horde centres of the Volga region in the 14th century are also found in 14th–15th century structures from Iran, Central Asia and Syria.

The coloured layer of the Kinski Vody mosaic fragments mainly consists of a white plum solid substrate base (slipware) with an upper coloured coating of white, blue (with different colour intensity), green, turquoise (both bright and light), yellow and red. Fragments of red and yellow colours have an easily-scratched matte surface, while others are shiny and dense. The yellow fragments feature a slightly different substrate, (white-blue instead of blue colouring and greater homogeneity). The green fragments are covered with a thin transparent layer of iridescent glass, reminiscent of chandelier glass.

The mineral, granulometric and chemical composition of the fragments – their base, substrate, and colour layer – were studied through photoluminescence, spectroscopic and spectral analyses. The use of spectroscopy proved to be uninformative. Therefore, only the data of the photoluminescence and spectral analyses are discussed below.

Results

Microscopic description and mineral composition

Full descriptions of the microscopic analyses and a table (Table 1) giving the composition of the samples be found in the [extended version of this paper](#).

We can distinguish three variants of tile production testifying to the multi-stage process. The base of all the Kinski Vody tiles is the same, possibly made from local alluvial river sediments. Ground gypsum was added to the mass for better binding, which sometimes crystallized during heating.

Seemingly identical sediments were also used to create substrates. However, there were two different variants of those substrates. One variant was used for white, blue, turquoise and green fragments. It is less dense and has larger grains. The other variant was used to make yellow and red mosaic. The latter required a denser substrate for cementing the coloured layer. This second method was necessary as the yellow and red coloured layer does not contain quartz material; it features only the pigment. Green fragments, additionally, are covered with a thin layer of quartz glass which protect the pigment.

Apparently, the process included a multistage heat treatment (firing) at different temperatures. The first stage involved making the base and firing. In the second, the base was covered with the substrate and fired (depending on the composition and the required resulting density of the substrate, different

temperatures were used). Thirdly, the substrate was covered with the pigment layer and fired (also at different temperatures because yellow fragments do not have a fused base paint, while there is some of it in red ones). The fourth step involved only green fragments and included adding the glass layer before a final firing.

Photoluminescence

The photoluminescence study revealed that samples could be divided into two different groups. The first includes examples in which the coloured layer is characterized by a luminescence similar to that of quartz glass: individual dots of blue colour on a general dark background. These are tiles with white, turquoise, or blue layers.

Samples from the second group (with yellow, red, or green layers) have brown luminescence. The yellow samples are slightly lighter than the red ones. The green ones are luminescent in the same way as the red ones (with dark brown light), but with lesser intensity. The luminescence of the second group is explainable by the presence of lead ochre in the pigments.

Ultimately, the two groups of photoluminescence support the idea that different methods of adding and cementing the pigment layer depend on the pigment composition.

X-ray spectroscopy

X-ray spectroscopy was carried out in the spectral laboratory of the Crimean Branch of UkrSGEI for 41 elements by chemical engineer Galina Rein. Full descriptions of the X-ray spectroscopy analyses can be found in the extended version of this paper at ([LINK](#)).

Results indicate that cobalt (samples 5 and 5a) was brought in from other places. Its non-typical high barium, phosphorus, arsenic and mercury content indicates a different type of deposit (formation of cobalt-bearing ores) and possibly a different mining area. The raw material of the mineral for paint (pigment for glazes) in samples 1, 1a, 4, 6, and 7 was likely polymetallic lead-tin ores. We know this as their oxidized parts often come to the surface of the glaze, where ore minerals undergo secondary transformations.

Interpretation and hypotheses

To compare these results with those from similar studies, I tried to find sources where similar methods were applied to kashi mosaics or similar fragments to those from Kinski Vody. Unfortunately, this was easier said than done. All researchers use different sets of situationally available methods; there is no unified set or protocol. However, some parallels can be traced. For example, the results obtained from Kinski Vody align well with the results of quantitative (X-ray) spectral analysis provided by Koval (2010) for what he calls “semifaience” turquoise glazes without additional decoration.

The classification and chronology for the glazed ceramics from Central Asia—including architectural materials—was carried out by Shyshkina (1979). She used technological features as the primary classification parameters. Starting from separating the building tiles as a distinctive set of artifacts, Shyshkina classified glazes and manufacturing techniques based on the manufacture period and the

location of the production center. She noticed that the composition of “architectural” and “tableware” glazes is practically indistinguishable and separated faience (kashi) without slipware and with white slipware from other groups.

Figure 5. Shakh-i-Zinda, 11th-15th century. Samarkand, Uzbekistan Image by Bobyrr, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0. Retrieved on 31.04.2024, available [here](#).

Figure 6. Namozgoh mosque, 17th century. Samarkand, Uzbekistan. A — general view; B — close-up of the mosaic. Image by Olena Vakarenko, used here with permission.

Due to the similarity of the “architectural” and “tableware” glazes, Shyshkina considers tiles to be a separate group only due to functionality. She indicates that “around the middle of the 13th century, as the faience kashi-ware spread around, potters used two types of blue (turquoise) glaze: opaque (for application to the loess-clay base) and transparent (for faience). See Table 2 in the extended version for comparison).

Glazed elements were not introduced into architectural decor prior to the second half of the 11th century. At first, they were made of clay mass shaped into rectangular tiles with white, blue (turquoise) and violet (possibly dark blue and cobalt, similar in colour to lapis lazuli) glazes.

From the second half of the 11th century, the appearance of cobalt dye in architectural decoration glazes is clearly recorded, including in Afrasiab, the ancient Sogdian capital, the legendary Marakanda (present-day Samarkand), where during the 11th century the extension and repair of the Shakh-i-Zinda mosque, glazed blue bricks with beveled long lateral planes (similar to those found at the Kinski Vody settlement) were used to decorate the mihrab’s wall. During the excavations of the citadel of Afrasiab, numerous uni- and bi-coloured bricks, as well as unicoloured rectangular, star-shaped, trapezoidal and triangular tiles were discovered together with the ornamental fragments similar to those found at Kinski Vody. Unicolour glazes on faience (kashi) were the most common ones in Sogd in the 8th – early 14th centuries. See Figures 5-6.

Glazes from Egypt and Syria have an unambiguously different composition than those of Iran and Iraq (Mason 2004). The latter are similar to those found in Ukraine, while the former ones used different raw materials. This is clear due to the differences in the composition of pigments (a different ratio of components and the composition of impurities) rather than through any clear differences in the clay or quartz sand of the tile bases.

The results obtained from Kinski Vody allowed for correlations with known pigments published by Mason (2004) (Table 3 in the extended version). A full discussion of these comparisons can be found in the expanded version of this paper.

Discussion

The chemical and mineralogical study outlined above offers some insights into the chain of glaze production. The Iranian Plateau as well as the vast territories of modern Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan (Buryakov 1974) was home to ore mining. It seems that the production of pigments as dry mineral-based powder mixtures was also confined to the mining locations. In its time of prosperity (late 11th to early 13th centuries), the Great Seljuk Empire--which included almost all of Iran and Iraq--captured Samarkand, Fergana and Bukhara and began the active construction of roads, caravanserais, madrasas and mosques. At the same time, the development of large mining deposits became more active, and the need for well-functioning trade routes for transportation increased.

As long as the Eurasian Steppe was divided between different nomadic groups, all caravans along the route were liable to be attacked and robbed. By paying different nomadic groups for the right to pass through their territory, and sometimes for temporary lodging, merchants found some measure of security along the route.

Khazanov (2022) believes that trade along the numerous fragmented Silk Road routes should be studied using a network approach. The changing nodes of a trade route network connected specific

traders linked directly to several such places in regional networks. Regional traders provided the bulk of the movement of goods via small caravans, while cities were transshipment points: some of the goods were sold locally, and some were delivered elsewhere by other merchants. Trade was segmented; each commodity passed through many hands from its place of production to the final consumer.

Long-distance trade flourished during the Mongol Empire, whose rulers, starting with Genghis Khan, tried to develop and support international trade and secure trade routes and foreign merchants. Merchants were allowed to use the Mongolian postal system (Yam), created for messengers and major officials. It was a time of significant unification of many trade routes. The Road carried not only silk and other high-status items from East to West, but also transferred religions, languages, crafts, craftsmen, scientific knowledge, technology, inventions, fashion, cuisine, metals, chemicals, minerals, plants, diseases and medicine (Khazanov 2022).

Such complex systems involved many people—merchants, guards, traders, interpreters and guides—who could function only through mutual trust. However, cases of fraud are also known and described in both scientific literature as well as works of fiction. If caught, the fate of a thief or fraudster was unenviable. There was no third option; those who wanted to trade and travel, trusted. Those who did not want to be punished, did not cheat or steal more than could be forgiven.

Thus, the mineral pigments extracted from the Iranian Plateau were crushed, abraded, mixed with aggregates and binders and sold. In the form of dry mixtures, they were transported to ceramic production places. Therefore, the chemical composition of the glaze of building and tableware ceramics along the Silk Road was identical while the technology of pigments, various additives, firing temperatures and the bases upon which the glaze was applied differed. In places where glazed wares were produced, glaze bases and substrates were made from local raw materials, which obviously caused some technological peculiarities.

In Samarkand, for example, the turquoise glaze was applied directly to building ceramics without creating a substrate (slipware). The base of ceramics here was predominantly made of clay (dense and massive). Perhaps, the glaze there was cheaper or of better quality (or maybe both), as the production was located closer to the source of raw materials.

In Ukraine, where sediments are looser, the base of mosaics fragments was loose and crumbly and made of sandy gypsum with an admixture of clay material. Therefore, the glaze would be less stable and durable. So before applying expensive imported dyes that arrived from the Iranian Plateau by way of the Silk Road, these fragments were covered with a white substrate mixture of finely crushed quartz-gypsum. Possibly, the slipware made from local materials allowed for a reduction of pigment consumption and a thinner layer of paint.

When taking into account the peculiarities of pigments applied to them, the multistage technology of mosaic tile production leads to two important ideas: 1) in Ukraine, the construction of Muslim cities was performed by experienced and skilful craftsmen, who understood the peculiarities of working with different substances well; 2) these craftsmen tried to ensure the maximum quality of the products they used, which would satisfy the customer and also use as little expensive imported raw materials as possible. By complicating the technology (i.e. by introducing additional operations, such as scratching and baking the base and applying a protective layer of lustre), masters tried to ensure the durability of the paint and the economic profitability of the process. It is obvious that the

complication and increase in labour inputs discovered in this study did not lead to a significant increase in cost. Raw materials were more expensive than the additional labour spent to save them.

Since the glazes studied in Ukraine and Central Asia differ in the amount of quartz and gypsum, it can also be assumed that the pigments mined on the Iranian Plateau were diluted in many locations: at resale points and at the locations of glaze production. They were sold by weight, so the sellers added quartz sand to the pigment bags, which they could not, did not have time to, or did not try hard enough to grind.

The key factors of this trade were time, trust and economic expediency. Both the seller, the intermediary, and the client were trying to get their own profit, but did not want to lose trust and trade relations, i. e. their reputation. Therefore, none of them allowed actions that would significantly deteriorate the quality of goods. Such a concern for reputation is indirectly confirmed by the fact that the more expensive, fine and difficult-to-use red, yellow, green and blue pigments were not diluted, unlike turquoise, the cheapest and most common pigment. See Figure 7.

Figure 7. Gradual change in the 14th-century mosaic colour from west (left) to east (right). A — Kinsky Vody; B — Bukhara (Masjidi Kalon); C — Samarkand; D — Turkestan. 1 — Images by Anna Radchenko; 2 — Image by Adam Jones, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0; 3 — Image by Bobyrr, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0; 4 — Image by Davide Mauro, licensed with CC BY-SA-4.0.

It is possible that the dyes were also mixed and diluted at the last station, where the goods were about to be used. For example, local craftsmen could dilute expensive pigments, saving them for later. This reduced the production costs while, apparently, still suiting the customer: transporting building tiles was prohibitively expensive. After all, the customer might not have known what the celestial turquoise should actually look like.

Conclusion

This overview (and the [full-text](#)) presents the most complete study of the glazes of architectural ceramics of the 14th century in Ukraine carried out with analytical methods. The composition of the base of mosaic tiles does not allow for conclusions about its origin, as – it is almost pure alluvial quartz sand. Some indirect signs suggest that the raw materials used for the base were local. The probability of local production is also confirmed by the findings of ceramic “pins” (used for ceramic firing) at the Kinski Vody settlement (Radchenko 2017). By contrast, the raw materials used for the production of glazes at Kinski Vody were not local. The composition of the studied glaze and available archaeological and geological data indicate that the raw materials could have been mined in the Iranian Plateau or

adjacent lands from Samarkand to Basra (which have similar geological formations). These raw materials came to Ukraine through a part of the Great Silk Road network (Khazanov 2022). The available data on the composition of the glazes allow us to assume the use of the common raw materials for its production in this territory. Technological differences seem to be caused not only by technological rationality but also by an economic one – that is, technology that depends on economic relations in the network of traders and the benefits, trust, and conventions between them.

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Research Overview

Antler allometry of the Irish Elk and the mystery of Stephen Jay Gould's data

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The Irish elk (*Megaloceros giganteus*) is one of the 'celebrities' of extinct megafauna. Its special status rests primarily on the gigantic size of its antlers—the largest ever known—that spread up to 4 meters for large stags. The huge antlers have generated an entire industry of fascinating stories. It has been said that the extinction of Irish elk is due to the antlers being overly large. Others have suggested that climate change prohibited the sustainable energy intake needed to grow enormous antlers every breeding season and that, coupled with the predation pressure of prehistoric humans (who displayed trophy antlers in their beautiful artworks) pushed the Irish elk to go extinction at c.a. 11,000 BCE. The fame is also partly due to the abundance of exceptionally well-preserved skulls and partial skeletons found in Ireland (a cause for the name of the animal, though it had quite a large range across Europe). Many of those remains have been reconstructed and stand at the main hall of museums around the world to greet visitors.

Eight years ago (May 15th of 2016), I was in Vienna visiting the Natural History Museum at the center of the city. The museum is situated next to the "Heldenplatz"—a significant place in recent European history where many important political actions took place. The museum building supports many beautiful, sometimes awe-inspiring sculptures in such an iconic European architecture style. Just like anyone else who traveled there from Japan (where I have my own cultural roots), seeing the Natural History Museum seems almost an end unto itself: a wonderful destination to take beautiful photos as souvenirs from a visit to the stunning city of Vienna. But my goal was different: instead of taking beautiful snapshots, I was in Vienna to take photos of hundreds of deer skulls. My May 2016 visit was the first trip of many that I carried out during my postdoc project (started earlier that same year).

Together with Prof. Thomas Hansen (University of Oslo) and many international collaborators, we aimed to revisit the classic work of Stephen Jay Gould, a prominent evolutionary biologist and a paleontologist. Gould conjectured that the antler size of the Irish elk *Megaloceros giganteus* was exactly as would be expected from their large body size (Gould, 1974, Gould, 1973). Gould's series of studies on the Irish elk constituted an important demonstration of his (then novel) idea that individual organismal phenotypes should be studied and understood in the context of the whole organism (Gould and Lewontin, 1979). This essentially means that large animals have longer limbs than smaller animals in order to support their body size. According to this logic, it is not the gargantuan legs of *Brachiosaurus* but rather the puny forelimbs of *Tyrannosaurs* that warrant scientific explanations. Broadly, the relationship between overall size of the organism and size of a part of the organism is called "allometry" (Huxley, 1932). Gould's research of the Irish elk became an icon of allometry study in evolutionary biology and related fields.

On the May 17th of 2016, I was invited by Dr. Frank Zachos, the curator of the Natural History Museum, Vienna into the entrance hall of the museum. Right next to the stairs, there was an entire skeleton of a male Irish elk. See Figure 8. I remember being very impressed as I looked up and up...and up. In fact, this was the first time I had ever actually seen the real physical remains of an Irish elk, rather than only representations of one! Though it might be surprising for some European archeologists, the Irish elk is not as well-known in Japan as it is in Europe. The sheer size and the magnificence of the antlers immediately struck me, who had no preexisting knowledge about the special status of the Irish elk among European museum goers. As I approached to get a closer look at the remains, I could see that the Irish elk male was also extremely well preserved. It is simultaneously intriguing and surprising that most well-preserved specimens of the Irish elk—including the individual in Vienna—were found in a single location in Ireland called Ballybetagh bog near Dublin (Barnosky, 1985). Current thinking is that the special anoxic layer of the peat bog there allowed for exceptionally favorable preservation conditions. What still remains a mystery is why hundreds of Irish elks were gathered there when they died. Coupled with the impressive antlers, such intriguing facts have invited many speculations regarding the evolution and extinction of the Irish elk (Worman and Kimbrell, 2008, Moen et al., 1999). Especially when juxtaposed with the historical backdrop, Gould’s conclusion about the evolution of Irish elk antlers was sensational.

Figure 8. The author measuring the Irish elk specimen on display at Museum of Natural History in Vienna on the 17th of May, 2016.

While the significance of Gould’s organismal and wholistic view of evolution is clear, my co-collaborators and I were not entirely convinced about the quantitative aspect of Gould’s conclusions regarding the evolution of Irish elk antlers. For one, the data Gould collected is of mediocre quality at the best, except for those of the Irish elk that Gould himself collected. Secondly, the statistical methods to estimate allometry from data that include multiple species have dramatically advanced since the 1970s. Consequently, the objective of this project was to assemble a new multispecies phenotypic data of body size and antler morphology from extant and extinct species of deer (Cervidae)—including the Irish elk—and analyze the data using formal phylogenetic comparative methods.

Visiting museum collections

Starting with the visit to Vienna’s Natural History Museum in May 2016, I visited nine museums located in Europe, the UK, the US and Japan over the subsequent two years. In total, we acquired data from 568 specimens covering 57 species and subspecies of Cervidae. Skull size (a proxy for total body mass in Cervidae; Damuth and MacFadden, 1990) was taken manually from the specimens, while the antler volume (a proxy for antler size) were obtained from 3D photogrammetry images of those specimens (details are described in [Tsuboi et al., 2020](#)). Cervidae are a wide group which have adapted to many different environments and display tremendous morphological diversity. Nevertheless, some noticeable specimens in our dataset stand out: 1) 24 specimens of the Irish elk *Megaloceros giganteus* from one locality (Ballybetagh bog), as mentioned above; 2) a complete skull with antler of a specimen of *Eucladoceros dicranios* from Florence, Italy (see Figure 9); 3) a reconstructed skull and antler of a fragmented specimen of *Sinomegaceros yabei* and 4) nine specimens of the recently extinct *Rucervus schomburgki* from Thailand.

Figure 9. A specimen of *Eucladoceros dicranios* on display at Museo di Paleontologia di Firenze.

Figure 10. Evolutionary allometry of antler volume on skull length. The dashed line is the allometry across 46 taxa from the family Cervidae and the solid line is across 18 taxa from the tribe Cervini. Both regressions are based on as many taxa as possible from the available data, but exclude *Muntiacus atherodes*, *Elaphodus cephalophus* and female *Rangifer*. Taxa not included in the regressions are marked with open symbols, and extinct taxa are marked with daggers. The regressions are based on phylogenetic generalized least squares including measurement variance and corrected for attenuation due to measurement variance in the predictor. The evolutionary model was an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process with a direct-effect predictor assumed to follow a Brownian motion. The cervidae model had an exponent of 5.95 ± 0.29 , and an intercept at the mean of $-15.16 \pm 0.05 \log(l)$ and the $R^2 = 90\%$. The diffusion variance for the predictor was $1.70 \log(\text{cm})^2/t$, where t is tree height. The cervini model had an exponent of 4.86 ± 0.35 , and an intercept of $-12.18 \pm 0.10 \log(l)$ and the $R^2 = 92\%$.

Was Gould right?

Our phylogenetic comparative analyses on the newly assembled data (Tsuboi et al., 2024) demonstrated that the picture surrounding the evolution of the Irish elk antler is much more nuanced than what Gould originally argued in his influential work (Gould, 1974, Gould, 1973). For example, we found that the allometric relationship, which sets the stage for what antler size should be considered normal for the group, critically depends on which varieties of deer are included in the calculations of allometry. Inclusion of small-sized deer species with rudimentary antlers (such as the genus *Pudu* from Latin America and *Muntiacus* from Southeast Asia) puts the Irish elk as expected relative to the allometry across the entirety of the Cervidae family. However, by sub-dividing the data to include only

“true deer” (the tribe Cervini), the Irish elk became a clear positive deviant from Cervini allometry. See Figure 10. While it remains an open question as to whether the allometry of Cervidae or Cervini should be used for the evaluation of the Irish elk antler size, Gould’s data did not include any species with rudimentary antlers. Gould himself (1974) argued in favor of analyses with the subfamily Cervinae, which is composed of Cervini (true deer) and Muntiacini (a tribe with rudimentary antlers). Thus, Gould technically limited his allometry analyses to include only Cervini. This led us to conclude that our new data and analyses ran counter to Gould’s argument about the size of the Irish elk antler. According to our results, the Irish elk’s antler volume was twice as large as would be expected from their body size and allometry.

The detective work and the remaining mystery

Subsequently, we set out to figure out the cause of the difference in our calculations as opposed to those presented by Gould. Not only did we analyze our own (new) data, but we also re-analyzed the exact same data Gould used for his study by recovering that information from the literature. For the most part, our detective work went smoothly. We were able to identify the causes of differences and discussed the pros and cons of different datasets and approaches. But there is one aspect in the discrepancies between our results and those of Gould that we are completely at a loss for explaining. Gould found that the scaling exponent (i.e., the log-log regression slope) of intraspecific allometry between antler size and skull size among ~ 79 adult specimens of the Irish elk is positive and similar to interspecific allometry of the corresponding traits. In contrast, our 24 specimens yielded no relationship at all.

One plausible explanation is that our data included only adult individuals in their prime as judged from tooth wear and circumference of the pedicel, a pair of appendages on the skull of male cervids that reflects individual age; (Tsuboi et al., 2024), whereas Gould’s data potentially included individuals from younger age classes. In Cervids, it is known that the size of antlers among males grow exponentially over their first 2-3 years of life; the growth plateaus once they reach their prime (Kruuk et al., 2002). Thus, if our data is a biased representation of prime-age adults, we might be able to explain the difference. However, Gould (1974) discusses the influence of age in his analyses (pp. 208) and pointed to several entries within his dataset that might represent either young or old individuals. Excluding those still appears to yield positive intraspecific allometry according to the figure presented in Gould (1974).

Unfortunately, Gould (1974) does not report measurements at the individual level. Thus, it is not possible to identify the causes of the difference more closely. However, speculations are possible. In terms of sample size, Gould’s Irish elk data is almost three times as larger as ours. One interpretation, therefore, is that our data was insufficient to recover the positive intraspecific allometry. However, we consider this to be unlikely because 1) the coefficient of determination in Gould’s data is high ($r^2 = 0.323$, Gould 1973, pp. 376) and 2) our volumetric data is of higher precision with respect to antler investment than Gould’s composite data based on a series of linear measurements. Thus, if Gould’s result is biological, our data should have sufficient power to detect the signal. However, it is possible that our data is simply qualitatively different from Gould’s data. For instance, while our data only contains specimens housed at museums, Gould measured individuals from private collections. Thus, there is a possibility that our data are different due to some kind of collection bias (Whitaker and Kimmig, 2020) between private and museum collections. Nevertheless, it is very difficult to imagine

how such an arguably subtle bias could have produced a sharp discrepancy in our estimate and Gould's estimate of intraspecific allometry.

Concluding remarks

Our evaluation of Gould's conjecture on the antler evolution of the Irish elk represents a tenuous juncture between what *can* be measured and what we *want to* understand—a dilemma of researchers who depend on retrospective analyses of historical materials, including paleontologists and archaeologists. Broadly, this is a problem of measurement theory: a branch of applied mathematics that concerns the relationship between measurements and reality (Voje et al., 2023, Houle et al., 2011). What we learned from our work is that novel technologies (like 3D photogrammetry) and advanced statistical methods (like phylogenetic comparative methods) are not always helpful for addressing measurement-theory problems. Personally, what turned out to be surprisingly helpful is the background knowledge of each specimen: where they come from, when and why they ended up there, sex and age of the specimen etc. that often come from a hand-written tag or even from a dialogue with museum curators.

Finally, I plan to further develop the [published dataset](#) as part of my own ongoing research. Given the identified mystery of Gould's data, I am particularly interested in expanding the data on the Irish elk measurements. If readers have any ideas about locations to find the Irish elk specimens outside the following museums (Natural History Museum in London, Museum of Natural History in Vienna, the Swedish Museum of Natural History and the National Museum of Ireland - Natural History), I would be very happy to hear.

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Project Overview

The Book of Deer

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Figure 11. Image of the Book of Deer, courtesy of Midas Media.

The year 2022 marked the temporary return of the Book of Deer (*Leabhar Dhèir*) to North East Scotland for the first time in several hundred years. The result of a successful NLHF grant and considerable local support, this return offered some 67,000 people the opportunity to view the Book, many for the first time (Book of Deer Project, 2023, p. 4). This contribution follows the trajectory of the Book from writing to temporary return, before concluding with a discussion of the concurrent archaeological programme.

The Book

The Book of Deer is a pocket gospel, with 86 folios and seven full-page illustrations. See Figure 11. The identities of the figures in said illustrations are unclear, though speculations as to the figures' identities

range from Abraham to God (Ellsworth and Ellis, 1994). The Book is around the size of a Penguin Folio text and contains the gospels of Matthew, Mark, Luke and John, though only the latter is complete (Cambridge Digital Library, n.d.). The Book is generally agreed to have been manufactured between 850 and 1000 AD, though it likely originated towards the earlier part of that range (Cambridge Digital Library, n.d.).

The origin of the Book is unclear – scholars have suggested it may have come from various places in both Scotland and Ireland, though there is no consensus as yet (Forsyth, 2008). The lack of clear origin does not detract from the Book's importance, though it does make certain claims and questions more complex (not least the long-term home of the text).

The Book currently resides in Cambridge University Library's Special Collections (Cambridge University Library, 2015). Joined by the Darwin notebooks (Paul, 2017) and Sumerian tablets (Cambridge University Library, n.d.), it is in excellent company!

The Gaelic

The Book of Deer is all the more remarkable as its addenda represent the earliest surviving written Scots Gaelic. These seven addenda are represented by added notes, written into the manuscript by different monks. These notes not only recontextualize our understanding of Scots Gaelic, but also help to situate the Book geographically. As the additions mostly take the form of land grants, they have also made it possible to situate the Book within the context of the (formerly lost) Monastery of Deer.

There are two particular outliers to the land grants. The first of these is a deed from King David I in favour of the monks of Deer and is dated (between 1131 and 1132 (Jackson, 1972, p. 36). The second references the figures of St. Columba and St. Drostan (the Monastery of Deer's founder) and concerns the foundation myth of the monastery (Jackson, 1972, p. 33). The rediscovery of this monastery will be discussed below.

Cambridge

The Book's trajectory from Aberdeen to Cambridge is largely unclear. It is reasonable to suggest that the Book moved from the monastery of Old Deer in Aberdeenshire (where the Gaelic addenda were written) to the adjacent Abbey following its completion in 1219, though there is little evidence to support this (Jackson, 1972, p. 1). From here, arguably the most curious part of the Book's complex journey, the tome moved to England, although when and where is distinctly unclear. We know that it ended up in Thomas Gale's collection in 1695 (Jackson, 1972, p. 8), before being gifted to John Moore, Bishop of Ely (Jackson, 1972, p. 8). Following Moore's death in 1697, George I purchased his library in its entirety, gifting it to the University of Cambridge in 1715 (Jackson, 1972, p. 8). From this point, Cambridge University Library held the text until 1860, when it was 'rediscovered' by librarian Henry Bradshaw (Jackson, 1972, p. 8).

Following its rediscovery, the Book of Deer enjoyed what could be argued to be a slow renaissance. After being the subject of Kenneth Jackson's Osborn Bergin Memorial lecture in 1970, the Book was exhibited in Glasgow in 1990 (Kaplan, 1990, p. 30) before being displayed in Cambridge in 2016 to celebrate the library's 600-year anniversary (Cambridge Digital Library, n.d.). The Book, and its 2017

excavation, were the subject of BBC Alba's first documentary on the subject, entitled [Air Toir Manachainn Dheir/The Lost Monastery of Deer](#) which was broadcast in 2018. Until 2022, the Book's last trip to Aberdeen was unknown.

The Return

Designed to coincide with Scotland's Year of Stories, we (Cameron and Jaspars) co-authored an NLHF grant to enable the temporary return of the manuscript to the North East for the first time in several hundred years (BBC News, 2022). This return lasted just shy of three months and ensured that some 67,000 people were able to view the Book, many for the first time (Book of Deer Project, 2023, p. 4). This return was not only valuable in terms of the quantity of visitors, but also in the quality of their visits. Many of the visitors remarked upon the emotional significance of the exhibition; some wept, some prayed, and one individual played bagpipes to the Book, in the understanding that "it would probably quite like that."

The return of the Book was supported by two further arms of the NLHF grant proposal – a cultural programme and ten-week excavation. The cultural programme ranged from jewellery making to banner creating and served to further the profile of the Book in the North East, bolstering the understanding of the text in the local area through heritage engagement.

Arguably the most important part of the proposal, was the ten-week period of excavations which were spread out over the course of the year. The excavations involved over 550 cumulative days of volunteering, and both furthered the profile of the text, as well as contributed towards community formation in the area.

The return of the text, and concurrent archaeological programme was supported by our second BBC Alba documentary entitled [Larach Leabhar Dheir/The Missing Monastery](#). This programme focused primarily on the 2022 excavation season, looking both at the archaeological work as well as the educational programme surrounding the text (Midas Media for BBC Alba).

From its conception, the project has held at its heart the desire to further strengthen a community around a text from which that community is geographically removed. It is our belief that community archaeology projects such as the one outlined below pay dividends; we all become better archaeologists and conduct better archaeology as a result.

The Archaeological Project

In 2008, a local group started searching for the lost monastery of Old Deer with geophysical surveys and annual excavations (which included local primary school classes). Cameron Archaeology became involved in 2014 and Jaspars joined the team in 2015. We re-focused the group into looking nearer the 1219 Abbey of Deer. See Figure 12. Rose Geophysics carried out an extensive ground penetrating radar and resistivity survey of the Abbey and surrounding areas. Though this highlighted some interesting areas, the results were not clear. We had to dig!

Figure 12. Drone photograph (facing east) showing Deer Abbey on the centre, the excavation area just above the modern road and Old Deer above right. Image © Midas Media.

Figure 13. The 11th-12th-century stone path fully revealed. Image © Midas Media.

In 2017 and 2018, we opened small trenches over a wide area. We uncovered a late 12th – early 13th century kiln, a 11th–12th century path (See Figure 13) and a 7th – 8th century posthole.

In 2022, we received a National Lottery Heritage Grant which included money for five months' excavation (which we spread over the year). As per usual, we included a large group of keen local (and some not so local) volunteers, archaeology students, school children and local clubs such as the Young Archaeologists' Club. The year's digging was fascinating: we worked our way down through garden soil to the furrows from rig and furrow cultivation and from stone foundations down to earlier structures, including more postholes.

The soil from these features was sent for processing to the University of Aberdeen's Department of Archaeology. The charcoal was sent to SUERC for radiocarbon dating. We were pleasantly surprised with the dates that came back. Nearly all the dates were in the early medieval period prior to the construction of the Abbey! This meant that we had found a group of post-holes (Figure 14) and a ditch (Figure 15) that were probably dug in the mid-7th to early 8th century AD, postholes and a hearth dating to the mid-10th – early 12th century and an east-west oriented line of three post-holes dating to c. 1150-1230. What this meant was that we had very likely found the remains of a wooden Cistercian building (possibly the church) which was likely in use while the stone church was being constructed.

Figure 14. Ditch section being recorded by archaeology students. Image © Cameron Archaeology Ltd.

Figure 15. A seasoned volunteer half-sectioning one of the post-holes. Image © Cameron Archaeology Ltd.

Figure 16. The Hnefatafl gaming board. Image © Michael Sharpe.

In another part of the site, we found an industrial area covered with charcoal and slag. Underneath were the remains of at least two mid-12th – early 13th century hearths associated with post-holes and stake-holes alongside the path mentioned above.

There were very few early medieval finds, but we did uncover a number of small stone gaming boards and gaming pieces, including a Hnefatafl board (a medieval strategy game; Figure 16). We recovered many finds that would have been associated with the post-1219 Abbey including both hand-made and wheel thrown pottery as well as a fragment of a urinal. Human bone fragments were recovered in one trench which had presumably been dumped, along with 19th century pottery, when the Abbey area was ‘tidied up’ by the landowners in the early 19th century.

Put together, these findings suggest at least three phases of medieval activity and intimate that we have found one part of a larger monastic site. While we did not find monastic vellum working areas, cross slabs or stone-working areas, church, graveyard, or domestic buildings, a drone shot of the site shows that this shallow valley of the South Ugie Water could have other monastic buildings hiding beneath the surface. A much larger geophysical survey and excavation is required. Nevertheless, as the site is buried under over half a metre of garden soil, it is well protected until future archaeologists can revisit the Deer site and uncover more of this important monastic locality.

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TEA Editor

Just One Damned Thing after Another © Accent Press

*Warning, spoilers ahead!

As you pack your rucksack for summer fieldwork, I highly recommend you save a spot for Jodi Taylor’s *Just One Damned Thing after Another* (2013, Accent Press, Ltd.). After a hard day working in the sun, it is the perfect way to wind down – especially if your trenchmates have been winding you up! The book is exactly what it says on the jacket: a new slant on history peopled by a madcap crew of strong (and often accident-prone) historians who carom around the past. They do not “do” time travel; instead preferring to describe their activities as the “investigation of major historical events *in contemporary time*”. Think about that for a second or two. You can imagine why working at St. Mary’s Institute for Historical Research would actually be every archaeologist’s dream job.

As one Dr. Madeleine Maxwell (‘Max’ to her friends, and the book’s heroine) arrives for her intake interview at St. Mary’s Institute for Historical Research, the director asks her the following questions: “...if the whole of history lay before you like a shining ribbon, where would you go? What would you like to witness?” As the director explains, St. Mary’s historians are sent into the past to observe and gather information. After they report back, their findings are revealed as the results of new scientific investigations. They work in partnership and are funded by the nearby “Thirsk University”. Of course, it is not a simple case of travel and retrieve; historians have a strict protocol of non-interference. This historical “Prime Directive” is actually self-enforcing. According to the director, History (referred to in the novels as a proper noun) has defence mechanisms. Historians who attempt to tweak the natural

unfolding of historical events are ruthlessly eliminated. As the director succinctly points out during the interview “How difficult is it to cause.... a block of stone to fall on a potentially threatening historian observing the construction of Stonehenge?”

Trainees require out-of-the-box thinking and the talent to speak multiple languages and blend in well. They must adapt quickly to new cultures and new places. They need to think fast, lie believably and have a certain knack for circumventing society’s rules. All of those quirks are ruthlessly tested during St. Mary’s rigorous training programme for prospective historians. That, alongside combat and survival training and—of course—time travel theory!

But historical knowledge plus a few specialisms is not enough to face off against the challenges of History, as any archaeological discussion down the pub on a Friday evening could tell you! In this area as well, Taylor’s novel does not disappoint. Of course, one needs to be appropriately dressed for one’s station and time period (no short hemlines, neon or Lycra at the turn of the last century, for example), but there are also certain technical issues that arise in historical research which require technical solutions. As the head of R&D at St. Mary’s puts it:

“...this is what I tend to think of as ‘practical’ history...The secret of Greek Fire? We’re on it. How did a Roman chariot handle? We’ll build you one and you can find out for yourself. What range does a trebuchet have? Exactly how far can you fling a dead cow? How long does it take to pull someone’s brains out through their nose? Any questions like that, then you come to me and we’ll find your answers for you!”.

The strong personalities at St. Mary’s are always blowing things up and hence are constantly removing the batteries from the smoke alarms (which annoys the Chief Technical Officer to no end). Pranks, high-jinks, and experiments abound. For example, we are told that one research team attempted to reproduce the Russian guns at the Battle of Balaclava during the Crimean War (made famous by Tennyson’s “The Charge of the Light Brigade”). Unfortunately, they miscalculated the range and ended up destroying the institute’s clock tower...

The book is like *Horrible Histories* for grown-ups. It is light reading and highly entertaining, but with a cool premise that, as the novel progresses, unfolds much further than outlined above. It also contains some spectacular ‘in-jokes’ for the historically-literate. These include teaching children the origin of the “v-sign” from the Battle of Agincourt, the rallying cry at Harfleur from Shakespeare’s Henry V (Cry God for Harry, England and Saint George), and name checking Anglo-Saxon rebel and guerrilla leader Hereward the Wake who fought against William the Conqueror in the fens of East Anglia.

Of course, there are conflicts and rivalries, drama, and a touch of romantic intrigue. As someone who is also *never* clean on site, what made me smile is the fact that Taylor seems to have gotten some aspects of the lives of those who work with the past right on the money, even if in a fantasy context. For example, after Max returns covered head to toe in filth from a dangerous mission, she is met by Farrell, the Chief Technical Officer:

“‘It went OK then?’

‘How can you tell?’

‘You’re all here. No one’s on fire. The pods are intact. There’s no screaming. An intelligent and perceptive man can read these small signs.’

I nodded. ‘Do you think I’ll ever meet one?’

He wiped my face with something cool. ‘I’m sure I saw you in a dress once. You were clean. And smelled good. Sometimes it seems like just a dream.’”

Pick up a copy for *après*-excavation (or for your beach bag!). It’s archaeological entertainment at its finest and perfect dream fodder until the EAA AM in August! I look forward to seeing you all there, with your Bucket List of must-see times and places in History inspired by *Just One Damned Thing after Another!*

Community Spotlight

Society of Africanist Archaeologists (SAfA)

Marina Gallinaro¹, Jorge de Torres¹, Anne Mayor² and Akin Ogundiran³

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The [Society of Africanist Archaeologists](#) (SAfA) is an organization of archaeologists, researchers from associated disciplines and others who share an interest in African archaeology and African societies. Originally founded as the Society of Africanist Archaeologists in America (SAAM) in 1971, it became an international association in 1988 and assumed its current name (Lubell, 1988). The membership is international, with participation from Africa, the Americas, Europe, Asia and Oceania. The Society is actively involved in research in many African countries.

SAfA's aims are:

To promote and to stimulate interest and research in the archaeology of the African continent.

To advocate and to aid in the conservation of archaeological resources.

To encourage public access to and appreciation of the aims, accomplishments and limitations of archaeological research.

To serve as a bond among those interested in African Archaeology, both professionals and non-professionals and to aid in directing their efforts into scientific activities.

To publish and to encourage the publication of archaeological research.

To discourage commercialism in archaeology and to work for its elimination (SAfA 2021).

SAfA is committed to supporting students and young researchers and promoting initiatives for African scholars. In recent years, it has supported the African Chronometric Dating Fund (ACDF) with several awards for scholars seeking to improve regional radiocarbon chronologies within the African continent, in collaboration with the PanAfrican Archaeological Association (PAA) and the British Institute in Eastern Africa (BIEA).

The Society holds biennial conferences devoted to African archaeology and related research topics. Since 1996, the meetings have alternated between Europe and North America, with two conferences held jointly with the Pan-African Association in Africa (2010 and 2014).

SAfA publishes a bulletin (*Nyame Akuma*), which appears twice a year and contains short reports on research projects around the continent. It recently marked its 100th issue (December 2023)! It is also the official sponsor of the *African Archaeological Review* and *Journal of African Archaeology*.

The SAfA mailing list is a valuable tool for updating the members' community on upcoming events, funding and calls for open job positions.

During the 23rd Annual EAA meeting in Maastricht, the former presidents (Eric Huysecom for SAfA and Felipe Criado Boado for EAA) signed a Memorandum of Understanding to collaborate on shared goals and to commit to ethical standards and professional developments. See Figures 17-18. This shared principle ensures that archaeological practices maintain high levels of integrity and respect for cultural heritage in both Africa and Europe (Rebay-Salisbury and Salisbury, 2017; Cornelissen, 2017).

Figure 17. EAA-SAfA meeting at the 24th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists in Barcelona. From left: Felipe Criado Boado, former President of the EAA; Marina Gallinaro, coordinator of the SAfA sessions; Eric Huysecom, former president of the SAfA; Stefano Biagetti, coordinator of the SAfA sessions; Alessandro Vanzetti, former member of the EAA board and chair of the EAA 2024 AM Organizing Committee. Photo by the EAA 2018 Social Media Team.

Figure 18. SAfA dinner at the the 24th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists. Photo courtesy of Stefano Biagetti.

Preserving archaeological heritage is a shared priority for SAfA and EAA. They are committed to safeguarding and maintaining the integrity of archaeological sites, artefacts, and landscapes. This involves addressing threats to heritage, whether from war, development, or other destructive processes. By working together, they aim to mitigate these threats and promote sustainable practices that ensure the long-term preservation of archaeological resources.

Since 2017, several SAfA sessions have been hosted at the EAA annual meetings and the number of papers focused on Africa presented at EAA sessions has increased. This contributes to facilitate the exchange of information and to create a robust framework for scientific collaboration that enhances the understanding of human history in Africa and Europe, fostering a deeper appreciation and protection of the diverse archaeological heritages.

The 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome will be another occasion to strengthen the dialogue and partnership among SAfA and EAA. The program includes six SAfA sessions focusing on various research fields, from Human evolution and Paleolithic Archaeology to neolithization and state formation, with a particular emphasis on the visual and symbolic world of ancient humans, combining different approaches from ethnography to bioarchaeology and digital imaging with a special focus on research sustainability. The number of papers focusing on African archaeological topics or case studies (more than 120!) is further confirmation of the success of this partnership. These papers are present in many sessions, covering all the thematic themes. We invite all to discover them!

Bibliography

Cornelissen, Els. 2017. "SAfA and EAA Memorandum of Understanding" *Nyame Akuma* 88: 6-7.

Lubell, David. 1988 "Editorial" *Nyame Akuma* 30: 1.

Rebay-Salisbury, Katharina and Salisbury, Roderick B. 2017. "Memorandum of Understanding with SAfA" *The European Archaeologist* 54: 2, 17-18.

Society of Africanist Archaeology. 2021. "By-Laws of the Society of Africanist Archaeologists (2021)" SAfA [online]. Accessed June 18, 2024.

Announcements

Photojournalism Competition

Are you *TEA*'s next photojournalist of the year?

Submit one image (photo or drawing) in **portrait*** format alongside a max 400-word text and find out!

Ranging from archaeology's early roots in cabinets of curiosities and the enthusiasm of Victorian antiquarians to the latest advances in GPR, molecular science and heritage practices, it is no secret that archaeology is a wide and varied discipline. We look at everything from rock art and pigments to isotopes, the experience of moving through the landscape and the values of contemporary communities. Is the study of the past a science, an art form or a social science? Various arguments support all of these options, but what do *you* think? Once again, *TEA* welcomes submissions to our photojournalism competition. We seek images that illustrate the great depth and breadth of archaeology and which include short answer essays on the following theme:

ARCHAEOLOGY: ART OR SCIENCE?

We have all been there—some excavators can turn a planum into a masterpiece while themselves completely covered in mud. Others work with pipettes, petri dishes and column chemistry whilst clad in pristine lab coats. Both are archaeology, and that is what we are after! Show us through pictures and text the joy and beauty in the art or science of *your* branch of archaeology!

How to enter:

Submissions should be made by email to tea@e-a-a.org by **1 August 2024 at 23:59 CET**. Each entry should include a single high-resolution (600 DPI) portrait-style image (.tif or .png) with an accompanying text (max 400 words).

The text should describe the subject matter of the photo, its location, archaeological relevance and a few lines relating it to archaeology as art or science (or both!). The text should be a .word file, and should also include a thumbnail of the image described. In your email text, please state your full name,

institution (if you wish it to be posted) as well as your EAA membership number. Please include 'TEA Photojournalism competition 2024' in the subject line of the email.

By submitting an image to the competition, you confirm that you have or have obtained copyright permission, that you provide permission for *TEA* to print the image in question as a cover, should your entry be among the winners and you also extend permission to the EAA to use the image with accreditation in its promotional materials.

What you can win:

The three winning entries will have their EAA membership fees waived for 2025 and will receive certificates describing them as "TEA Photojournalist of the Year 2025". The images will feature on the winter, spring and summer issues of *TEA*, and will be announced as *TEA*'s Photojournalists of 2025.

Rules of the competition:

You must be a current EAA Member to enter.

Each Member may submit only one entry, so choose wisely.

You may only submit an image on your own behalf.

The image must be oriented in portrait to potentially fit the cover of a future *TEA* issue.

You must have copyright permission for the image and you must agree to provide permission to *TEA* to reprint the image. This includes the possibility of the image being included in a future issue of *TEA* spotlighting the entries of the competition.

All subject material which answers the competition theme will be considered, though it must also be appropriate to being a cover of *TEA*.

Judging criteria:

After closing date, all submissions will be evaluated by a panel (including both professional photographers as well as archaeologists). Those short-listed will be notified by end of August that their entry has been selected for the second round of the evaluation process, which will be by popular vote by Members of the EAA. Before the voting begins, shortlisted entries will be spotlighted on EAA's social media channels alongside their texts before the final vote. Winners will be notified by end of October.

***Please note that images which are not in portrait orientation will not be accepted. If you have an image that you would like to contribute that is square or in landscape format you must crop it to portrait format before sending it in to the competition.**

New edition of ‘The History of the British Fauna’ short course at the University of Sheffield (16-18 Sept 2024)

Contributed by organizers Angela Maccarinelli, Phoebe Liu and Lenny Salvagno

Image © Sheffield Zooarchaeology, used here with permission.

The Sheffield zooarchaeology team is returning with a fresh edition of the face-to-face short course **‘The History of the British Fauna: wild and domestic vertebrates’!**

From the **16th to the 18th of September 2024**, this three-day course offers an opportunity to gain a basic knowledge of the development of the British fauna from the Pleistocene to the Modern day. You will learn about various topics, ranging from evolution, zoogeography, domestication, introductions, and extinctions, and explore the dynamic interactions between humans and animals throughout history. By the end of the course, participants will have a comprehensive understanding of what species are native and which animals have been introduced in Britain, and how animals have adapted to changing environmental conditions and increasing human interference. Mammals, birds, fish, amphibians and reptiles will all be included.

Teaching will be delivered through short lectures and hands-on practical activities. This course is not aimed at professional and/or experienced zooarchaeologists but is directed to students, professionals, and enthusiasts and does not require any previous knowledge in zooarchaeology or previous participation in any of our short courses.

To book a place in 'The History of the British Fauna: wild and domestic vertebrates' short course, please follow [this link](#).

If you would like to know more about our short courses, please visit us on our [webpage](#), or follow us here:

Facebook: Sheffield Zooarchaeology Short Course

Instagram: @zooarchlabsheff

Twitter: @zooarchlabsheffield

Alternatively, you can always get in touch directly by email at: zooarch-shortcourse@sheffield.ac.uk

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